

How to use SolACE's microbial consortia formulated with DCM Minigran® technology in the field

Problem

European agriculture is challenged by the need to produce more crops using less fertilizer inputs (mainly nitrogen and phosphorus) and with more frequent or intense periods of drought.

Solution

Microbial inoculants are agricultural amendments containing beneficial microorganisms (bacteria or fungi) that promote plant health or growth. Within the SolACE project, microbial inoculants have been selected for improving growth of bread wheat and potato crops under combined nutrient and water shortages. Carriers adapted to the selected microbial inoculants were developed to ensure survival over time and easy application by the farmers. DCM Minigran® technology has been used to develop granular carriers of these selected microbial inoculants (Fig. 1). A recent potato greenhouse trial performed by University of Hohenheim (Germany), applied Minigran® consortia in a standard drought stress screening system. Potatoes grown from true seeds showed positive trends regarding plant growth promotion and improved tuber development. Also, better results were obtained after a consortium application, leading to a reduction of drought damage.

Benefits

DCM Minigran® technology allows to:

- develop granular microbial inoculant formulations with complex consortia of fungi and bacteria for synergistic effects on plants,
- optimize microbial shelf life by a specifically engineered Minigran® composition and formulation,
- apply all selected microbial inoculants in a single application step and close to the seeds or seed tubers, reducing the number of microorganisms needed,
- employ existing machinery such as microgranule spreaders,
- comply with European Union regulation of organic farming,
- and grow more resilient plants under nutrient-stress and drought conditions.

Applicability box

Theme

Crop growth, water- and nutrient-use efficiency, reduced fertilizer

Geographical coverage

In areas of cereal and potato cultivation with a continental climate

Application time

All year round

Required time

At sowing

Period of impact

Actual crop

Equipment

Microgranule spreaders

Best in

Specific crops - Bread wheat and potatoes

Figure 1: Example of granular formulation developed with the DCM Minigran® technology (photo courtesy: DCM). For SolACE, granule dimension is 1-2mm. Each granule contains each of the selected microorganisms.

Practical recommendation

- To apply the granules developed with the DCM Minigran® technology, check the label for storage conditions and shelf life, and comply with all recommendations regarding their utilization, application methodology and dosage.
- These recommendations are likely to be different depending on the microbial inoculants present in the granules and their concentrations.
- General recommendation for the granular microbial inoculants developed within the SolACE project:
 - Storage: cool and dry storage, ideally at 4°C. Do not freeze.
 - Application at sowing in furrow or directly in contact with seeds/seed tubers at 30 kg/ha.
 - Application can be done using a microgranule spreader (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Example of Minigran® application at sowing using a microgranule spreader (photo courtesy: DCM)

Remark: Currently, microbial consortia formulated with DCM Minigran® technology within the framework of the SoACE project can solely be used for research purposes within the SolACE project. Minigran® products containing other microbial inoculants are however available for sale. Please contact DCM directly or your local representative.

Use the comment section on the [SolACE discussion forum](#) to share your experiences with other farmers, advisors, and scientists!

If you have any questions concerning the method, please contact the first author of the practice abstract by e-mail.

Further information

Videos

- [Minigran: The wonder granule](#)

Weblinks

- [More information on Minigran](#)

About this practice abstract and SolACE

Publisher:

De Ceuster Meststoffen, n.v. (DCM)

Bannerlaan 79, 2280 Grobbendonk, Belgium.

Phone +14257357

Authors: Michelle Van Dyck

Contact: mvd@dcm-info.com

Permalink: zenodo.org/record/5159671

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SolACE: The project is running from May 2017 to April 2022. The goal of SolACE (Solutions for improving Agroecosystem and Crop Efficiency for water and nutrient use) is to help European agriculture face major challenges, notably increased rainfall variability and reduced use of N and P fertilizers

Project website: www.solace-eu.net

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